

THE ESSENCE OF A SYSTEMATIC APPROACH TO MANAGEMENT IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *This article examines the theoretical and practical aspects of the systemic approach in managing preschool educational organizations. The essence of the systemic approach, its pedagogical, organizational and psychological foundations are highlighted, and the role of this approach in increasing management efficiency is analyzed based on scientific sources. The main principles, stages of the systemic approach and the difficulties encountered in its implementation are also discussed.*

Keywords: *integration, integrity, flexibility, effectiveness, stages of implementing the systemic approach, planning stage, organizational stage, optimization of resources (material, human and technological), development of cooperation between teachers and parents, implementation stage. application of modern technologies and innovative methods in implementing the educational process, monitoring and evaluation stage.*

Introduction.

From a systems theory perspective, the concept of "Development of the preschool education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" was developed in our republic by Resolution No. PP-4312 dated May 8, 2019. The concept defines the goals, objectives, priorities, medium-term and long-term stages of development of preschool education in the Republic of Uzbekistan and serves as the basis for the development of programs and comprehensive measures aimed at developing the preschool education sector. [1]

Within the framework of educational governance, implementation of work on the management, planning and organization of the organization of preschool education creates the necessary, but not sufficient conditions for the effective integration of the efforts of the members of the educational organization's team. It is known from practice that the work that people actually do does not always meet the official requirements imposed on them. A characteristic feature of public organizations is that people joining them, having their own reasons, are able to set goals for themselves. They may want to do something or not and work accordingly. When people come to an organization, they want it to allow them to realize their interests. If this does not happen, they either leave the organization or do not fully mobilize their potential and talents.

Methodology.

According to contemporary models, if the joint activity is well planned and organized, it will be successful only if the performers know what, where and how to do until some internal and external conditions change, requiring adjustments to this process. These changes can jeopardize the implementation of planned actions or, conversely, open up new opportunities. Management must respond to the changes in a timely manner, and for this it must have information about them.

In order to obtain such information and determine the need to make adjustments to the work process, it is necessary to carry out a special management action called control.

This topic emerges from a growing need to control, management acquires the most important component without which it cannot function - feedback. Control makes management "insightful" and receptive to changes. The reaction to these changes is carried out through planning, organization and management. As a result, the management cycle becomes closed. Planning, organization, management and control have a complex structure and consist of many other activities. For example, it may include planning, situation analysis, forecasting, setting goals, evaluating performance, making decisions on choosing one or another version of the work plan. Management is the process of setting tasks for subordinates, analyzing the state of the team, evaluating the work of subordinates, making decisions on rewards and punishments, informing employees, resolving conflict situations, etc. [2]

Results and discussion.

It is crucial to note that the preschool education system is an important stage in the comprehensive development of children. The effectiveness of this process largely depends on the organization's management system. A systems approach ensures the quality of education by organizing the interconnected and integrated activities of all components. This article discusses the scientific and theoretical foundations of the systems approach and its practical application.

The essence of the systems approach has been studied by many scientists. This approach is based on a comprehensive understanding of the management process:

- Bertalanffy (1968), having developed the theory of systems, emphasized that the components of any system are interconnected.

- L.S. Vygotsky noted the importance of a systems study of the factors influencing the development of preschool children.

- Yu.K. Babansky (1982) showed that the systematic management of the educational process plays an important role in the effective organization of the pedagogical process.

Principles of a systems approach in preschool education

1. Integration: the interconnectedness of all components.
2. Integrity: the focus of the pedagogical and management process on a single goal.
3. Adaptability: the ability to quickly respond to external changes.
4. Effectiveness: the focus of all processes on specific results.

Stages of implementing a systems approach

1. Planning stage. Defining the goals and objectives of the educational organization. Defining the role of each employee.

2. Organizational stage. Optimization of resources (material, personnel and technological). Development of cooperation between teachers and parents.

3. Implementation stage. Using modern technologies and innovative methods in the implementation of the educational process.

4. Monitoring and evaluation stage. Evaluation and analysis of the process efficiency. Identification of deficiencies and taking measures for improvement

A systems approach can be used in preschool educational organizations in the following areas:

- Child development monitoring system: diagnostics and monitoring to ensure an individual approach.

- Working with teaching staff: training teachers and developing motivational programs.

- Cooperation with parents: harmonization of educational work with the family environment.

Problems arising during the implementation of a systems approach

1. Lack of resources (financial, personnel and material).
2. Insufficient knowledge and skills of teachers in the field of a systems approach.
3. Poor communication within the organization.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the use of a systems approach in preschool educational organizations is important for improving the quality of the educational process. To do this, the following recommendations should be implemented:

- Organization of trainings on a systems approach for teachers and managers.
- Implementation of a monitoring system to take into account the individual needs of children.
- Integration of innovative technologies into the management system.

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